

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF PREPARING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS FOR CREATIVE ACTIVITY.

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Abstract: In this article, the ways of forming the creative activity of primary school students, the preparation of students of junior school age for the process of creative activity, its pedagogical importance, the methodology of developing creativity in students, and how to make children of the present age creative Brief measures aimed at increasing speech to thinking are given.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship and intellectual development, Practical training, Connection with the outside world, Presentation and creative works, Experiential learning

The main part: the topic "Pedagogical content of preparing primary school students for creative activities" is very important. Pedagogical content related to this topic includes the following elements:

Entrepreneurship and intellectual development: In order to develop the creativity of elementary school students, tasks and activities related to their business and intellectual development are prepared.

✚ Practical classes: Classes are organized for students to implement their acquired knowledge by turning theoretical knowledge into practice

✚ Connection with the outside world: Students are given activities and tasks related to the outside world that develop their creative potential.

✚ Presentations and creative works: Presentations and creative activities are organized for students to prepare their creative works.

✚ Experiential teaching: Part of the pedagogical content includes teaching based on students' acquired knowledge and experiences.

✚ These pedagogical contents are important for the development of students' creativity and creative potential and help to implement their acquired knowledge.

In the development of creative activity, the use of forms and methods of organizing scientific activity related to knowledge, which leads to creative ability, scientific and creative research, gave its results. In this regard, classes for the development of creative activity include dialogue classes, discussions, debates,

conversations, fantasy, research classes, classes for setting problems and solving them; Participatory classes, modeling, artistic and technical creativity, creating, creating small discoveries, writing essays, making chronicles, using business games, innovative methods were the most effective. in the educational process, it is held at a certain time of teaching as game methods of lesson forms.

Conclusion: In this thesis, we presented some ways of developing the creative activity of young schoolchildren, but they are promising. for its development, as we see, a lot. Now the choice depends on the individual inclination of each teacher. is a way of organizing your learning activities.

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